

***In-silico* Mechanics of Mini-PCDH15 Proteins Provide Insights into Inner-Ear Tip-Link Function[#]**

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[#] *Data presented here are part of a separate study in preparation tentatively titled "Elasticity and Thermal Stability are Key Determinants of Hearing Rescue by Miniaturized Protocadherin-15 Proteins" by De-la-Torre et al.,*

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In addition, we show data from Ivanchenko et al., (Nature Communications, 2023) and Choudhary et al., (PNAS, 2020).

Abstract. Inner ear sensory hair cells rely on “tip links” formed by protocadherin-15 (PCDH15) and cadherin-23 (CDH23) to transduce mechanical stimuli from sound and head movements into receptor potentials. PCDH15 has 11 extracellular cadherin (EC) repeats and a membrane adjacent domain (MAD12) with calcium ions binding at the junctions of consecutive EC repeats to stiffen the ectodomain and stabilize its overall structure. Nonsense mutations in PCDH15 result in Usher syndrome type 1F (USH1F), causing profound hearing loss, balance disorders, and progressive blindness. Although gene therapy using adeno-associated virus (AAV) vectors could be therapeutic, PCDH15's large size (~5.8 kbp) exceeds the carrying capacity of AAV vectors (~4.7 kbp). To address this issue, we shortened the wildtype PCDH15 ectodomain by eliminating up to five EC repeats while retaining important functional domains in eight rationally designed mini-PCDH15 versions (V1 to V8). Our previous experimental data (Ivanchenko *et al.*, 2023) show that mini-PCDH15-V4 can restore hearing in *Pcdh15*-knockout (KO) mice, while mini-PCDH15-V7 is partially effective, and mini-PCDH15-V8 is ineffective. Here we describe the assembly of experimentally supported mini-PCDH15 models obtained from both X-ray crystallographic structures and AlphaFold2 predictions. We used these models with all-atom molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to study their mechanics. Our models and simulations offer an atomic-resolution view of mini-PCDH15 dynamics and mechanics suggesting mechanistic principles that underly tip-link function and that may guide the optimization of novel mini-PCDH15s for USH1F gene therapy.

INTRODUCTION

Hearing is a fundamental sensory process in vertebrates. In mammals, it involves the capture of mechanical waves (sound-induced vibrations) by the pinna, which are then transmitted through the ear canal to the tympanic membrane (ear drum). The ear drum vibrates and passes on the mechanical waves to the three ossicles in the middle ear, which amplify the sound vibrations and send them to the cochlea - a fluid-filled, snail-shaped structure located in the inner ear. Here, the organ of Corti contains numerous cochlear hair cells that are sensitive to mechanical force and are responsible for mechanotransduction [1-6]. At the apical end of these hair cells, there are several rows of stereocilia (actin-filled protrusions) arranged in a staircase-like pattern, which form bundles that respond to force stimuli. Adjacent stereocilia are connected by thin protein filaments known as tip links [7-8]. The deflection of these stereocilia in response to sound vibrations results in tension on the tip links, which in turn leads to the transient opening of an ion channel located at the apical surface of the lower stereocilium [7-10], where potassium and calcium ions flow through the channel into hair cells, leading to depolarization. This further results in the release of neurotransmitter at the base

of hair cells, producing nerve impulses recognized by the central nervous system [11]. Importantly, the formation of tip links involves the interaction between two atypical members of the cadherin superfamily, cadherin-23 (CDH23) and protocadherin-15 (PCDH15) [12], which have a cytoplasmic, transmembrane, and extracellular domains featuring 27 and 11 extracellular cadherin (EC) "repeats", respectively. The calcium-dependent functional and structural integrity of the tip links is important, as the complex dissociates upon removal of all calcium ions [9]. Moreover, the mechanism underlying the interaction between these two proteins has been well characterized, with EC1 and EC2 of each protein interacting in an antiparallel, overlapped handshake fashion [13-14].

Structural differences throughout PCDH15's ectodomain. The elasticity and response to force stretching of PCDH15 is predicted to depend on its sequence and the number of calcium ions bound to linker regions between consecutive EC repeats [15-17]. In addition to having 11 EC repeats, PCDH15 also has a membrane adjacent domain (MAD12) that connects to its transmembrane domain [18-19]. Computational and experimental studies have been conducted to examine the flexibility and elasticity of the complete PCDH15 ectodomain [14, 20-21]. The interaction between the PCDH15 EC1-2 repeats and the CDH23 EC1-2 repeats, which form a handshake complex, is particularly important for maintaining the integrity of the tip links. The linker regions between EC repeats of PCDH15 contain variable calcium-binding motifs. While the EC1-2 linker region binds three calcium ions at canonical calcium-binding sites with a DXNDN motif, the EC2-EC3 linker region that contains an atypical calcium-binding motif only binds two calcium ions [14]. Additionally, the EC3 repeat plays a significant role in parallel dimerization of PCDH15 [14, 22], facilitated by EC2-3 repeats, resulting in the formation of a heterotetramer with two PCDH15 EC1-2 + CDH23 EC1-2 handshakes [14]. In the middle region of PCDH15, the EC3-4 linker region [17], with an atypical calcium-binding motif, binds two calcium ions and its slightly bent conformation provides enhanced flexibility to the full ectodomain [14, 17]. Conversely, the EC4-5 linker region has three canonical calcium-binding sites and is considered rigid [14]. The EC5-6 linker region, with a PPNNQ motif, binds only one calcium ion at site 3 in EC6, providing enhanced flexibility for the tip-link complex [14]. The EC6-7 and EC7-8 domains have canonical linker regions similar to EC4-5. The EC8-EC9 linker region near the C-terminal ectodomain of PCDH15 binds three calcium ions, although it is not considered as completely canonical [16]. The EC9-10 linker (HPGEEI) is calcium-free. The EC9-EC10 repeats can be in a bent conformation that contributes significantly to the flexibility and elasticity of the tip-link complex [16]. The C-terminal domain of PCDH15 includes the canonical EC10-EC11 linker region with three bound calcium ions, and a L-shaped arrangement of EC11-MAD12. Similar to EC2-3, the EC11-MAD12 fragment is involved in parallel dimerization of PCDH15 [18]. In summary the PCDH15 canonical linker regions that bind three calcium ions are found in EC1-2, EC4-5, EC6-7, EC7-8, and EC10-11. In contrast, the atypical linker regions are EC2-3, EC3-4, EC5-6, and EC9-10, which bind either two or one calcium ions, or none at all in the case of EC9-10.

Usher syndrome type 1F. Hearing and vision are important for human life. Usher syndrome (USH), the most common deaf-blindness syndrome, is a genetic condition causing deaf-blindness in individuals below the age of 65, accounting for 50% of such cases, characterized by symptoms such as hearing impairment, retinal damage in the form of retinitis pigmentosa, and a lack of vestibular responses [23-24]. This syndrome is usually divided into three clinical types (USH1, USH2, and USH3) with various subtypes caused by different mutations in different genes. In this work, we focus on a subtype of USH1, namely USH1F, which is caused by nonsense mutations in the human PCDH15 gene and characterized by profound hearing loss, balance deficit, and progressive blindness [25-27]. These mutations result in dysfunction of tip links essential for inner-ear mechanotransduction.

Adeno-associated virus (AAV)-based gene therapy in the treatment of USH1F. Gene therapy is an attractive therapeutic strategy for the treatment of USH1F. The process of gene therapy involves the introduction of genetic material into target cells using viral or non-viral transporters. The aim is to correct or replace the defective or missing gene, thus restoring normal function to the target tissue or organ [31-34]. Progress in gene therapy has established AAVs as a widespread delivery tool for addressing single-gene inherited diseases. The low toxicity and immune response triggered by these viruses reduce the chances of harmful side effects and facilitate sustained expression of the transgene [28-30]. Moreover, different AAV serotypes and variants possess a wide range of specificities, yet each has its own unique preference for certain cell types [31-34]. The development and identification of new capsid structures have significantly enhanced the rate at which AAVs can transduce cells, particularly within neural tissues [28-36]. However, AAV-based gene therapy is limited by its size-carrying capacity, which typically allows the delivery of ~4.7 kb of genetic material.

Dual-AAV vectors strategy and mini-PCDH15 approach. AAV-based gene therapy is a promising treatment for USH1F. However, due to the size limitations of AAV vectors, the full-length coding sequence of the PCDH15 gene, which is ~5.8 kb in length, must be reduced to fit within a single AAV vector for gene therapy. To address this challenge, previous strategies have employed the use of dual AAV vectors to deliver parts of the full-length PCDH15 protein separately to the cochlea of *Pcdh15*-knockout (KO) mice [35]. However, dual AAV vectors often exhibit lower levels of complete transgene expression than single AAV vectors. To overcome this limitation, we have developed a

"mini-PCDH15" approach [37], which involves rationally engineering and truncating the PCDH15 wildtype (WT) ectodomain by removing 4-5 EC repeats while retaining important domains, such as EC1-2 for binding to CDH23, and EC2-3 and EC11-MAD12 for parallel dimerization (Table 1). By utilizing this approach, the size limitation of the single AAV vector strategy can be effectively overcome with less issues related to the expression level of the transgene, providing a viable and more effective alternative for the treatment of USH1F.

TABLE 1. Designs of engineered mini-PCDH15 proteins. Adapted from [35]

	TM+ CD	MAD12	EC11	EC10	EC9	EC8	EC7	EC6	EC5	EC4	EC3	EC2	EC1	bps
V1						X	X			X				4383
V2							X	X	X					4443
V3							X	X	X	X				4080
V4						X	X	X	X	X				3756
V5				X	X	X				X				4035
V6				X	X			X	X					4095
V7				X	X			X	X	X				3729
V8				X	X	X		X	X					3750

Experimental results of mini-PCDH15 proteins. Experimental evidence has demonstrated the potential of mini-PCDH15 proteins to ameliorate hearing loss in *Pcdh15*-KO mice. Despite the absence of structures for the engineered linkers, our colleagues [37] have conducted *in vivo* tests of three mini-PCDH15 versions (V4, V7, and V8) containing key domains (EC1-3 and EC11-MAD12) for binding to CDH23 EC1-3 as well as parallel dimerization (Table 1). Specifically, *Pcdh15*-KO mice were administered AAV vectors carrying different versions of mini-PCDH15 transgenes, and then the hearing sensitivity of both control and KO mice was assessed using auditory brainstem response (ABR) tests. Mini-PCDH15-V4 showed the ability of near-complete restoration, mini-PCDH15-V7 exhibited partial functional rescue, and mini-PCDH15-V8 displayed no functional rescue [37] (Fig. 1a). This study [37] contributed evidence supporting the potential of mini-PCDH15 proteins as a therapeutic strategy for hearing loss in humans, which warrants further exploration and validation using computational and experimental approaches.

The elasticity of the complete PCDH15 ectodomain monomer has been predicted by steered molecular dynamics simulations. In a previous study conducted by Choudhary *et al.* [14], the full human and mouse PCDH15 ectodomains bound to their corresponding CDH23 EC1-2/3 partners were successfully constructed using overlapping crystal structures of PCDH15 fragments. Short molecular dynamics (MD) equilibrations followed by constant-velocity steered MD (SMD) simulations on the entire ectodomains of monomeric and dimeric human and mouse PCDH15 were used to explore their conformational dynamics and elasticity. Stretching speeds were as slow as 0.02 nm/ns close to physiological values for basilar membranes exposed to high-frequency loud sound [38]. The results of the simulations indicated that after monomeric ectodomain straightening, the stretching of EC5-6 (one calcium ion) and EC9-10 (calcium free) linker regions was observed first, followed by the unrolling and unfolding of the MAD12 domain at a force peak of approximately 331 pN at 0.1 nm/ns for human PCDH15 and approximately 356 pN at 0.1 nm/ns for mouse PCDH15 (Fig. 1b). Notably, during this process, the CDH23 EC1-2/3 remained bound to the PCDH15 EC1-2. The effective spring constant of the first phase of the straightening of the ectodomain was ~3.3 mN/m for human PCDH15 at 0.1 nm/ns, with a 10 nm extensibility, and approximately 1.5 mN/m for mouse PCDH15 at 0.1 nm/ns, with a 15 nm extensibility. During the second phase of the stretching of EC5-6 and EC9-10, the effective spring constant was approximately 24.4 mN/m for human PCDH15 at 0.1 nm/ns, with a 5 nm extensibility, and approximately 27.5 mN/m for mouse PCDH15 at 0.1 nm/ns, with a 5 nm extensibility [14]. These findings shed light on the conformational dynamics and elasticity of the PCDH15 ectodomain and provide insights into the mechanical properties of the tip-link complex.

FIGURE 1. Hearing rescue by mini-PCDH15 proteins and PCDH15 elasticity. (a), *Pcdh15*-KO mice were injected with an AAV vector for delivery of the mini-PCDH15 gene. ABR tests shows that V4 and V7 partially rescue the hearing of *Pcdh15*-KO mice, while V8 does not work at all. Adapted from [35]. (b), Force versus end-to-end distance for constant-velocity SMD simulation of human PCDH15 EC1- MAD12 domain + CDH23 EC1-2 at 10 nm/ns (purple and blue), 1 nm/ns (bright green and cyan), and 0.1 nm/ns (dark green and turquoise, 10- ns running averages shown in black and maroon; grey lines are fits used to determine elasticity of the complex). Adapted from [20].

Elasticity of mini-PCDH15 proteins. In a separate study (De-la-Torre *et al.*, 2024), we used experimentally supported mini-PCDH15 models built using both X-ray crystallographic structures and AlphaFold2 predictions coupled with all-atom MD simulations to predict their *in-silico* mechanics at atomic resolution. Equilibrium MD simulations show that the mini-PCDH15-V7 EC3-EC7 linker is the least rigid and most flexible among mini-PCDH15 engineered linkers. SMD simulations reveal that the monomeric mini-PCDH15-V4 closely mimics the WT monomeric PCDH15 elasticity because of the presence of a bent EC9-EC10 linker. In contrast, mini-PCDH15-V7 and -V8 lack a WT-like soft extension phase and exhibit smaller force peaks and diminished extensibility than mini-PCDH15-V4. Overall, these models and simulations offer an atomic-resolution view of mini-PCDH15 dynamics and mechanics suggesting mechanistic principles that underly tip-link function and promote the use of a rational and structure-based mini-gene approach to develop AAV-mini-gene therapies for other large cadherin proteins. Here we present how we assembled the mini-PCDH15 models that were used for simulations.

RESULTS

We assembled models of the full ectodomain of monomeric mouse mini-PCDH15 proteins by integrating crystal structures of PCDH15 [13-18] along with engineered linker regions in COOT [39]. Two strategies were used to obtain structural models of engineered linker regions. In the first one, AlphaFold2 [40] was used to predict them. These predictions were done without using a structural template in a Colab notebook (ColabFold v1.5.5, Google research) [41]. In the second, we aligned known crystal structures and built the engineered linkers of mini-PCDH15 proteins manually by connecting the N and C termini of EC repeats in COOT.

For the mini-PCDH15-V4 with engineered linker EC3-EC9, we utilized the crystal structure of PCDH15 EC1-3 (Fig. 2a, in purple) in complex with CDH23 EC1-3 (Fig. 2a, in blue), incorporating the connecting linker sequence (p.366DENNQ) found between WT PCDH15 EC3 and EC4. This assembly was then connected to the crystal structure of PCDH15 EC9-MAD12 (Fig. 2a, in lime) by aligning the C α atoms of the last two residues (p.369NQ) from p.366DENNQ (WT EC3-EC4 linker sequence) to the C α atoms of the last two residues (p.900DY) from p.897DMNDY (WT EC8-EC9 linker sequence). Finally, we deleted p. 900DY and regularized the engineered linker region in COOT. A similar process was consistently used across all alignment-based (AL) versions of mini-PCDH15 proteins (mini-PCDH15-V7 AL in Fig. 2b; mini-PCDH15-V8 AL in Fig. 2c). The six-resulting mini-PCDH15 models were labeled mini-PCDH15-V4 AF2, mini-PCDH15-V4 AL, mini-PCDH15-V7 AF2, mini-PCDH15-V7 AL, mini-PCDH15-V8 AF2, and mini-PCDH15-V8 AL. To mimic canonical Ca²⁺ binding, engineered linker regions in all versions were modeled with two Ca²⁺ ions.

FIGURE 2. Assembly of monomeric mini-PCDH15 ectodomains. (a), Assembly of mini-PCDH15-V4 AL model. Crystal structure of CDH23 EC1-3 is in blue, of PCDH15 EC1-3 is in purple, and of PCDH15 EC9-MAD12 is in lime. We manually connected the C-terminal end of PCDH15 EC1-3 to the N-terminal end of PCDH15 EC9-MAD12. Engineered linker region is highlighted in a black box. (b), Assembly of mini-PCDH15-V7 AL model. Crystal structure of CDH23 EC1-3 is in blue, of PCDH15 EC1-3 is in purple, of PCDH15 EC7-EC8 is in lime, and of PCDH15 EC11-MAD12 is in brown. We manually connected the C-terminal end of PCDH15 EC1-3 to the N-terminal end of PCDH15 EC7-EC8 and the C-terminal end of PCDH15 EC7-8 to the N-terminal end of PCDH15 EC11-MAD12. Engineered linker regions are highlighted in black and red boxes. (c), Assembly of mini-PCDH15-V8 AL model. Crystal structure of CDH23 EC1-3 is in blue and of PCDH15 EC1-4 is in purple. Crystal structure of PCDH15 EC7 is in lime, and of PCDH15 EC11-MAD12 is in brown. We manually connected the C-terminal end of PCDH15 EC1-4 to the N-terminal end of PCDH15 EC7 and the C-terminal end of PCDH15 EC7 to the N-terminal end of PCDH15 EC11-MAD12. Engineered linker regions are highlighted in black and red boxes.

DISCUSSION

We have used the experimentally supported mini-PCDH15 models obtained using AF2 or aligned X-ray crystallographic structures to carry out all-atom MD simulations to study their structural stability, molecular properties, dynamics, and mechanics. These results are described in a separate study by De-la-Torre *et al.* Our quantitative analysis of equilibration simulations confirmed the structural stability of these engineered linkers. In addition, the EC3-EC7 linker of mini-PCDH15-V7 AL exhibited the highest inter-repeat flexibility among the engineered linkers. Conversely, both the AF2-predicted and AL-based EC7-EC11 linkers of mini-PCDH15-V8 demonstrated the lowest inter-repeat flexibility. Notably, when comparing the rigidity of the engineered linkers to both canonical (EC1-2 and EC10-11) and non-canonical (EC2-3 and EC9-10) linkers in the WT PCDH15 protein, the mini-PCDH15-V7 EC3-EC7 linkers were identified as the least rigid, suggesting its potential to enhance the extensibility of mini-PCDH15 V7 under mechanical tension.

Steered MD simulations indicated that the elasticity of mini-PCDH15-V4 closely resembles that of WT PCDH15, primarily due to the presence of a bent EC9-EC10 linker. This resemblance encompasses an initial soft phase, marked by the unbending of the calcium-free EC9-EC10 linker, and a subsequent stiff stretching phase characterized by the extension of various EC linkers, culminating in the extension of the entire protein chain and the unrolling and unfolding of MAD12. These phases exhibit elasticity metrics comparable to those of WT PCDH15, perhaps explaining why mini-PCDH15-V4 can restore hearing in *Pcdh15*-KO mice [35]. Conversely, mini-PCDH15-V7 lacks the initial soft phase and has only the stiff stretching phase observed in WT PCDH15, supporting its partial efficacy in restoring hearing in *Pcdh15*-KO mice. Mini-PCDH15-V8 is also distinguished by the absence of an initial soft phase and showed significantly increased rigidity and reduced extensibility compared to mini-PCDH15-V4, aligning with its inability to rescue hearing in our previous *in vivo* gene therapy trials [35]. Our steered MD simulations underscore the essential role of the native EC9-EC10 linker in enabling mini-PCDH15 constructs to fully rescue hearing in *Pcdh15*-KO mice.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Xinyue, Deng]: As mentioned in the discussion, steered MD simulations indicated that the stiffness of mini-PCDH15-V4 is very close to the wildtype. I am curious about this result because v4 is one-third shorter than the WT. Shouldn't it be stiffer than the WT even with the EC9-10 kink?

[Haosheng, Wen]: Thank you for the good question, Xinyue. The elasticity of both the WT PCDH15 and Mini-PCDH15-V4 is determined by the softest elastic element, EC9-10. During the SMD simulations, mini-PCDH15-V4 exhibited a two-phase stretching behavior similar to that of the wildtype (WT) PCDH15. The initial soft phase is primarily characterized by the unbending of the Ca²⁺-free EC9-EC10 linker region, with an effective spring constant comparable to that of the WT PCDH15. This soft phase is succeeded by an extension of the WT EC2-EC3 and EC9-EC10 linker regions, followed by the stretching of the entire protein chain, resulting in an effective spring constant akin to that observed during the hard pulling phase of WT PCDH15. As previously mentioned, these findings support the conclusion that Mini-PCDH15-V4 possesses WT-like elasticity.

[Xinyue, Deng]: In the introduction, it is written "there are three rows of stereocilia." To my understanding, the number of rows of stereocilia can depend on the type of hair cell, so perhaps "several rows" would be better?

[Haosheng, Wen]: Thank you Xinyue, you are correct. We have revised the manuscript accordingly.

[Xinyue, Deng]: In the "structural differences throughout PCDH15's ectodomain" section it is written "The EC9-10 linker (HPGEL) is not calcium-free.", I believe this may be a typo because it is later mentioned that EC9-10 linker is calcium-free.

[Haosheng, Wen]: Thank you Xinyue, it is a typo and we have revised the manuscript accordingly.

[Xinyue, Deng]: In the results section, it is written "by aligning the C α atoms of the last two residues ... (WT EC3-EC4 linker sequence) to the C α atoms of the last two residues ... (WT EC8-EC9 linker sequence)." Should the second "last two residues" in the sentence be "first two residues" because it seems to be linking the N-terminal of EC9-MAD12?

[Haosheng, Wen]: Thank you Xinyue, the residues mentioned are indeed at the N-terminal end of EC9, but these are also the last two residues of the mentioned sequence. Mini-PCDH15-V4 possesses an engineered EC3-EC9 linker region, where we aligned the C α atoms of the last two residues (p.369NQ) from p.366DENNQ (WT EC3-EC4 linker sequence) to the C α atoms of the last two residues (p.900DY) from p.897DMNDY (WT EC8-EC9 linker sequence), leading to a new linker sequence p.366DENNQDY. Finally, we deleted p.371DY in the aligned structure.

[Araya-Secchi, Raul]: It will be very interesting to see a more detailed structural comparison between the mini-PCDH15 variants (V4, V7, V8) and wild-type PCDH15.

[Haosheng, Wen]: Thank you Raul, further structural and simulation results of mini-PCDH15 proteins are reported in: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2024.06.16.599132v1.full>.

[Araya-Secchi, Raul]: Also, and perhaps this will be covered in the coming publication, a more detailed discussion regarding why some work and some do not and how the mechanical properties of the mini-PCDH15 might change under different conditions, such as varying calcium concentrations or different types of mechanical stress.

[Haosheng, Wen]: Thank you Raul, a more detailed discussion on why mini-PCDH15-V4 works is also covered in: <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2024.06.16.599132v1.full>.

[Araya-Secchi, Raul]: Are there plans to obtain structures of the Mini-PCDH15 proteins?

[Haosheng, Wen]: We have solved crystal structures of the engineered EC3-EC7 and EC4-EC7 linkers.

[Araya-Secchi, Raul]: How are the linkers being designed? Is there an interest in exploring with different linkers in terms of length and composition?

[Haosheng, Wen]: The engineered linkers were designed based on truncating the PCDH15 WT ectodomain by removing 4-5 EC repeats while retaining important domains, such as EC1-2 for binding to CDH23, and EC2-3 and EC11-MAD12 for parallel dimerization. We are working on new versions of mini-PCDH15 proteins with different length and composition.

[Araya-Secchi, Raul]: Can you speculate on the effect of adding more copies of the bent EC9-10 pair instead of the partial calcium binding repeats?

[Haosheng, Wen]: This is a very interesting question. Firstly, due to the size constraints of a single AAV vector, there is limited capacity to incorporate an additional copy of the bent EC9-EC10 repeats. However, if an extra pair of EC9-EC10 were to be added to Mini-PCDH15-V4, the resulting sequence would be EC1-EC2-EC3-EC9-EC10-EC9-EC10-EC11-MAD12. Given that the Ca²⁺-free EC9-EC10 repeats are the primary contributors to the elasticity of WT PCDH15, this modification essentially results in connecting two identical springs in series. According to Hooke's law, the extension x of a spring is related to the force F by the equation:

$$F = k \times x \quad (1).$$

For each spring in the series, the extension due to the Force F will be:

$$x_1 = \frac{F}{k} \text{ and } x_2 = \frac{F}{k} \quad (2).$$

The total extension x_{total} of the system is the sum of the extensions of individual springs, which is given by

$$x_{total} = x_1 + x_2 = \frac{F}{k} + \frac{F}{k} = \frac{2F}{k} \quad (3),$$

and it is related to the force F by Hooke's Law:

$$F = k_{total} \times x_{total} \quad (4).$$

Finally, we get the effective spring constant

$$k_{total} = \frac{k}{2} \quad (5).$$

Thus, incorporating an additional pair of EC9-EC10 into mini-PCDH15-V4 would likely result in a softer derivative of the protein.